

Survey Questions

Questions	Response options
In politics we often talk about 'left' and 'right'. How would you classify the Green Party on a scale from 1-11, where 1 means the party is 'left' and 11 means the party is 'right'? You can use the values in-between to grade your opinion.	1 - 11
And what about yourself? Where would you position yourself on a scale, where 1 is 'left' and 11 is 'right'?	1 - 11
The general delegate assembly in Münster decided to introduce several new ways for members to participate: The <i>Mitgliederbegehren</i> and the <i>Mitgliederbefragung</i> . How do you think this decision will affect your own participation? <i>Mitgliederbefragung</i> <i>Mitgliederbegehren</i>	Will participate less Will participate the same Will participate more Don't know
How often have you done participated in these activities in the last six months? Discussed relevant topics Wrote proposals for assemblies Supported proposals for assemblies Discussed proposals for assemblies Voted as grass-roots member in a working group or members assembly Voted as a delegate, at a delegate assembly or national working group Worked in party bodies	Not at all Once 2-5 times 6-10 times More often Don't know
Through which channels did you do participate in these activities?	At local meetings or assemblies At national meetings or assemblies At non-localised meetings (Skype, telephone conference) Via Mail / Fax On Social Media (Facebook, Twitter etc.) On party owned platforms online (Antragsgrün, Wurzelwerk etc.) Other
Please rank the following sentences based on their importance for party-internal democracy (highest ranking first)	All members can participate in votes All members can participate in discussions All members can participate equally All members can participate as much as possible
Which gender do you classify as?	Male Female Other No response
How old are you?	below 18 18-29 30-39 40-49 50-59 60-69 70+ No response
What is your highest education qualification?	None Still at school Secondary School (Volks-/Hauptschule) GCSE (Realschule) A-Levels (Fach-/Hochschulreife) University degree or national diploma PhD No response

Which state are you resident in?	Baden-Wuerttemberg Bayern Berlin Brandenburg Bremen Hamburg Hessen Mecklenburg-Vorpommern Niedersachsen Nordrhein-Westfalen Rheinland-Pfalz Saarland Sachsen Sachsen-Anhalt Schleswig-Holstein Thuringen Abroad No response
What type of area do you live in?	In a large city (above 100.000 inhabitants) In the suburbs of a large city (above 100.000 inhabitants) In a small town (between 10.000 and 100.000 inhabitants) In the countryside (below 10.000 inhabitants) No response
What is your current occupation?	None Student Employed for wages Self-employed Civil servant Retired Unemployed Homemaker No response
How regular do you use the internet?	Not at all Every month Every week Every day All the time No response
Do you hold any positions or mandates, or have you done so in the past?	Have a position or mandate Had a position or mandate in the past Never had a position or mandate
At which level?	Europe National State Region District Local